

Chemical Examination of *Streblus asper*

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Streblus asper, commonly known in Bengal as 'Sheora' belongs to the family *Moraceae*. The isolation of an α , β -unsaturated lactone from the root bark of this plant was reported earlier¹ and recently a large number of cardiac glycosides have been isolated by Manzetti and Reichstein² from the same source.

The chemical examination of the stem bark of *S. asper* has recently been taken up in this laboratory. Air-dried powdered stem bark of *S. asper* was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). The solvent was distilled off and the residue was taken up in ether and was separated into acidic and neutral parts in the usual way. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over a column of silica gel when four crystalline compounds having m.p.s 223-24°, 213-15°, 136-37° and 98-100° respectively were obtained besides a fraction (Fraction A) which showed two spots in TLC. The first three crystalline compounds were identified as α -amyirin acetate, lupeol acetate and β -sitosterol³ respectively by m.p., mixed m.p. and TLC (TLC carried out according to the method of Barua *et al.*⁴) and I.R. spectra. Fraction A was found by TLC to be a mixture of α -amyirin and lupeol. Acetylation of Fraction A followed by column chromatography over silica gel furnished α -amyirin acetate and lupeol acetate. The compound having m.p. 98-100° was shown to be a diol. It did not give any colour with tetranitromethane indicating the absence of unsaturation in this compound. Its I.R. spectrum showed bands at 3180 cm^{-1} and 3250 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl groups. Combustion analysis and molecular weight determination by Rast's method suggested a molecular formula, $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$, for the diol. The mass spectrum of the diol, however, did not show any peak for the molecular ion but there was a peak at m/e 362 for the $\text{M}-2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ion.

Further work on the constitution of this diol is in progress.

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